

STRUCTURAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE “MUSLIM WORLD” CONCEPT

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Abstract: The identification of the concept as mental entity, marked by the linguistic specificity, is a natural step in the establishment of the anthropocentric paradigm of humanitarian linguistic knowledge. The "Muslim World" concept is an integral part of the "Religious World" concept and serves as a significant component of the linguacultural world picture. The aim of this article is to conduct dictionary analysis of the concept “Muslim world” and to identify the conceptual features of lexemes “Muslim” and “World” separately. The study was based on five English dictionaries: 1. Macmillan English Dictionary: for advanced learners (MED). 2. Longman Advanced American Dictionary (LAAD). 3. Oxford Advanced Learner’s Dictionary (OALD). 4. Merriam-Webster Dictionary (MWD). 5. Cambridge Dictionary (CD). The results of lexemes` denotative meanings` analysis were presented in the form of graphs by distinguishing conceptual features leading to the final structural characteristics.

Keywords: lexeme, concept, conceptual feature, notional component, conceptosphere, denotative meaning, dictionary analysis.

Annotatsiya: Kontseptning lingvistik o'ziga xoslik bilan ajralib turadigan aqliy subyekt sifatida aniqlanishi gumanitar lingvistik bilimlarning antropotsentrik paradigmasini o'rnatishdagi tabiiy qadamdir. “Musulmon olami” kontsepti “Diniy olam” tushunchasining ajralmas qismi bo‘lib, til va madaniy dunyo manzarasining muhim tarkibiy qismi bo‘lib xizmat qiladi. Maqolaning maqsadi “Musulmon olami”

tushunchasining lugʻaviy tahlilini oʻtkazish, “Musulmon” va “olam” leksemalarining konseptual xususiyatlarini alohida aniqlashdan iborat. Tadqiqot beshta ingliz lugʻatiga asoslangan: 1. Macmillan English Dictionary: for advanced learners (MED). 2. Longman Advanced American Dictionary (LAAD). 3. Oxford Advanced Learner’s Dictionary (OALD). 4. Merriam-Webster Dictionary (MWD). 5. Cambridge Dictionary (CD). Leksemalarning denotativ maʼnolarini tahlil qilish natijalari yakuniy tuzilish belgilariga olib keluvchi konseptual xususiyatlarni farqlash yoʻli bilan grafiklar koʻrinishida keltirildi.

Kalit soʻzlar: leksema, kontsept, kontseptual xususiyat, tushunchaviy komponent, kontseptosfera, denotativ maʼno, lugʻaviy tahlil.

Аннотация: Идентификация концепта как ментальной сущности, отмеченной языковой спецификой, является закономерным шагом в становлении антропоцентрической парадигмы гуманитарно-лингвистического знания. Концепт «Мусульманский мир» является составной частью концепта «Религиозный мир» и выступает значимым компонентом лингвокультурной картины мира. Целью данной статьи является проведение словарного анализа концепта «Мусульманский мир» и выявление концептуальных признаков лексем «Мусульманский» и «Бир» по отдельности. Исследование основано на пяти английских словарях: 1. Macmillan English Dictionary: for advanced learners (MED). 2. Longman Advanced American Dictionary (LAAD). 3. Oxford Advanced Learner’s Dictionary (OALD). 4. Merriam-Webster Dictionary (MWD). 5. Cambridge Dictionary (CD). Результаты анализа денотативных значений лексем были представлены в виде графиков путем выделения концептуальных признаков, приводящих к итоговым структурным характеристикам.

Ключевые слова: лексема, концепт, концептуальный признак, номинальный компонент, концептосфера, денотативное значение, словарный анализ.

INTRODUCTION.

The identification of the concept as mental entity, marked by the linguistic specificity, is a natural step in the establishment of the anthropocentric paradigm of humanitarian linguistic knowledge. The concept is understood as a multidimensional thought construct, reflecting the process of understanding the surrounding reality, the result of human activity, experience and knowledge about the world, preserving information about it. The main function of the concept is the function of replacing not only the basic meanings of the word, but also all possible variants and shades of use [1, 2010].

“All concepts can be transferred by a set of language tools, each of which reveals only concepts` part” [10, 2010]. Accordingly, the concept “Muslim world” is understood as a multi-dimensional culturally marked mental-affective entity, has a conceptual, figurative and value meaning and is activated in the discourse by heterogeneous lingual means.

MAIN PART.

Whatever the orientation of the concept, in any case it is always the basis for both: cognition and the studied culture. It is appropriate to consider linguacognitive and linguacultural concepts as related concepts, as two different vector mental entities with an emphasis on different aspects of human experience.

Modern cognitivists assert that the content of a concept is inexhaustible, and even if all linguistic means are taken into account, this will only give us a general picture [7, 2016; 9, 2004].

Let us turn to the definitional analysis of the concept “Muslim World”. As our research is based on the concept analysis through modern English speaking media discourse, let us analyze the denotational meaning of the lexeme “Muslim” in English dictionaries. The study was based on five English dictionaries:

1. Macmillan English Dictionary: for advanced learners (MED).
2. Longman Advanced American Dictionary (LAAD).
3. Oxford Advanced Learner’s Dictionary (OALD).

4. Merriam-Webster Dictionary (MWD).

5. Cambridge Dictionary (CD).

Let us familiarize with the definitions in these dictionaries.

Macmillan English Dictionary: for advanced learners: Muslim - someone whose religion is Islam. Synonyms and related words: Allah, ayatollah.

Longman Advanced American Dictionary: Muslim - someone whose religion is Islam.

Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary: Muslim - believing in and practicing Islam; connected with the religion of Islam (a Muslim family, a Muslim name). The dictionary presents the following examples:

- For example, Muslims are proud that Islam is the fastest growing religion in the West.
- Islam requires that all Moslems do what they can to defend Islamic lands when under attack from non-Moslems.
- An Islam without Muslims then becomes a museum piece rather than a living faith.

Merriam-Webster Dictionary: Muslim - a person whose religion is Islam. A follower of Islam. A believer or follower of Islam, an adherent of Islam. Synonyms: Islamist, Mohammedan, Moslem, Muhammadan, Muhammedan.

Cambridge Dictionary: Muslim - a person who follows the religion of Islam.

In the Merriam-Webster Dictionary we found the etymology of the word "Muslim": Origin of Muslim: Arabic muslim, literally, one who submits (to God). First Known Use: circa 1615.

On the basis of the obtained data it is possible to conclude that dictionaries define the concept of "Muslim" primarily as a person - a follower of a certain religion. The data obtained can be presented as a table [see Table. 1]. When identifying a conceptual feature, we put the sign "+" (if the value of the word is present in the dictionary) or "-" (if the meaning of the word is absent):

Table 1. Conceptual features of the lexeme “Muslim”

Dictionary	Macmillan	Longman	Oxford	Merriam-Webster	Cambridge
Conceptual feature					
Someone with Islamic religion	+	+	+	+	+
believing in and practicing Islam	—	—	+	—	—
a follower of Islam	—	—	—	+	—

Conducted conceptual analysis, including etymological and component analysis based on dictionary definitions, gives the opportunity to present the core of the concept “Muslim” as “someone whose religion is Islam”.

Next, let us study the lexeme “World”, using for analysis the English dictionaries mentioned above.

Macmillan English Dictionary: for advanced learners presents the following definitions: WORLD: 1. the planet that we live on: We observe changes in the world's climate. 2. society in general, in all countries: We want to guarantee our children a safer world. 3. a particular group of countries: It is the oldest institution in the English-speaking world. 4. used about a particular society at a particular time in history: This library was one of the wonders of the Ancient World. 5. used about the particular type of place or situation in which someone lives or works: Children feel powerful in the world of imagination that they create. 6. mainly literary: the state of being alive.

Longman Advanced American Dictionary defines that WORLD: 1. the planet we live on, and all the people, cities, and countries on it; earth: At that time China was the most powerful country in the world. 2. the society that we live in and the kind of life we have: We thought we could change the world then. 3. a particular area of activity or work and the people who are involved in it: the fast-paced business world. 4. a

particular group of countries or part of the world: Our public schools are among the worst in the developed world. 5. a particular period in history and the society and people of that time: the world of the Anglo- Saxons. 6. a particular type of place or situation: Truong found himself living in a world of poverty and uncertainty. 7. the life of a particular or group of people lives, especially the things they do and the people they know: Alvin's world was full of dance and music. 8. the animal/plant/insect world animals, plants etc. considered as a group of living things with their own particular way of living or behaving. 9. a planet in another part of the universe where other things may live: strange creatures from another world. 10. the way of life most people live, rather than a spiritual way of life: John renounced the world when he became a monk.

In the Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary we found: **WORLD**: 1. the earth, with all its countries, peoples and natural features: to sail around the world. 2. a particular part of the earth; a particular group of countries or people; a particular period of history and the people of that period: the Arab world; the English-speaking world. 3. a planet like the earth: There may be other worlds out there. 4. the people or things belonging to a particular group or connected with a particular interest, job, etc: the animal/plant/insect world; the world of fashion. 5. everything that exists of a particular kind; a particular kind of life or existence: the natural world (= animals, plants, minerals, etc.). 6. a person's environment, experiences, friends and family, etc: Parents are the most important people in a child's world. 7. our society and the way people live and behave; the people in the world: We live in a rapidly changing world. 8. a way of life where possessions and physical pleasures are important, rather than spiritual values: monks and nuns renouncing the world. 9. the state of human existence: this world and the next (= life on earth and existence after death)

Merriam-Webster Dictionary presents the following definition for the “world”. **WORLD**: 1a. the earthly state of human existence. 1b. life after death —used with a qualifier (the next world). 2. the earth with its inhabitants and all things upon it. 3. individual course of life: career. 4. the inhabitants of the earth: the human race. 5a. the

concerns of the earth and its affairs as distinguished from heaven and the life to come. 5b. secular affairs. 6. the system of created things: universe. 7a. a division or generation of the inhabitants of the earth distinguished by living together at the same place or at the same time (the medieval world). 7b. a distinctive class of persons or their sphere of interest or activity (the academic world) (the digital world). 8. human society (withdraw from the world). 9. a part or section of the earth that is a separate independent unit. 10. the whole body of living persons: public (announced their discovery to the world). 11. kingdom (the animal world). 12. a celestial body (as a planet).

Cambridge Dictionary defines the term “World” as followed: **WORLD**: 1. the Earth and all the people, places and things on it: Different parts of the world have very different climatic conditions. 2. a group of things such as countries or animals, or an area of human activity or understanding: the Muslim World; the modern/industrialized world; the animal world. 3. a planet or other part of the universe, especially one where life might or does exist: There was a man on the news last night who reckons we've been visited by beings from other worlds.

As for the etymology of the word “world” - from Old English “woruld” means human existence, this world, age.

Having analyzed five English dictionaries, we can conclude that there are similarities and differences in the definition of the word “world”. All analyzed data is presented in the form of graph in the Table 2. The presence of a conceptual feature is marked with the sign “+” (if the value of a word is present in the dictionary) and absence with “-“ (if the meaning of a word is absent):

Table 2. Conceptual feature of the lexeme “World”

Dictionary	Macmillan	Longman	Oxford	Merriam-Webster	Cambridge
Conceptual feature					
our planet/all people	+	+	+	+	+

society	+	+	+	+	—
area of activity/work	—	+	+	+	+
group of countries	+	+	+	—	+
period in history	+	+	+	+	—
type of place/situation	+	+	+	+	+
the animal/plant/insect world	—	+	+	+	+
place like the earth	—	+	+	—	+
person's life	—	+	+	+	—
not religious	—	+	+	+	—
human existence	—	+	+	+	—
public	—	—	—	+	—

The conducted conceptual analysis, which includes etymological and component analysis based on dictionary definitions, gives the opportunity to present here the core of the concept “world” as “the planet that we live on”.

Thus, the core of the concept “Muslim World” is a collection of all those people on the planet, whose religion is Islam, as well as their followers. On the basis of the above we can say that the interpretation of the concept “Muslim World” combines in itself terms that have descriptive character towards the mentioned concept. If we combine the conceptual meanings of both words, we can come to the conclusion that the English vocabulary explains the concept “Muslim world” as everything that describes the phenomenon of the Muslim world: these are lexemes for everyday life and psychology, culture and ethnography, objects of material and phenomena of spiritual worlds.

The analysis of the above definitions shows that our focus is on a certain group of people (community, generation) who are linked by common ideas, particular interest, job [OALD]; a particular area of activity or work and the people who are involved in it [LAAD]; a distinctive class of persons or their sphere of interest [MWD]. It also follows from these definitions that the existence of the concept “Muslim world” requires the presence of a particular period in history and the society and people of that time [LAAD]; a particular period of history and the people of that period [OALD]; generation of the inhabitants of the earth distinguished by living together at the same place or at the same time [MWD], which, in turn, implies the existence of a certain lifestyle, which is determined by the dictionary definitions such as the life of a particular or group of people lives, especially the things they do and the people they know [LAAD]; the particular type of place or situation in which someone lives or works [MED]; the way people live and behave [OALD]. In this case the feature of Muslim lifestyle/culture is formed as a result. The Shariah, as a set of religious, legal and domestic norms, which every Muslim must follow is a Muslim way of life. Hence, the feature “lifestyle/culture” of Muslims is the equivalent of the term “Shariah”. The Shariah is the religious and ethical foundation of Islam, which will also include work, everyday life, norms of people’s behavior. One cannot but agree with the fact that a Muslim way of life cannot be achieved without characterizing the activities and way of life of the Prophet Muhammad. The image of the prophet Muhammad, his activities are ideal for all believers.

The lifestyle of Muslims, in turn, allows us to judge the existence of such a feature as “ceremony and rituals” which serves as certain conditions of realization for a particular way of life (a particular type of place or situation; the kind of life we have (LAAD)). It should be clarified that this very feature "ceremony and rituals" serves as a correlate for all possible actions necessary for the religious practices. In order to create such conditions, it is necessary to have certain knowledge and skills, and knowledge in Islam is regarded as a human duty and dignity.

It should be further noted that “The Muslim World” characterizes the environment of the individual, that is his/her family, friends (a person’s environment, experiences, friends and family [OALD]; the society that we live in [LAAD]). This allows us to identify another feature such as society. The main value for Muslims is the family and the hierarchy of relations within the family. The foundations of justice and social status are laid initially in the family, and then passed on and implemented in society. Hence the mandatory characteristic “socium” is the conceptual correlate of the society surrounding the Muslim.

Consequently, the analysis of the definitions of the concept “Muslim world”, given in modern English-language explanatory dictionaries, allow us to conclude that the “Muslim world” concept has obligatory features, namely lifestyle/culture of Muslims, ceremony and rituals which serve as conditions of realization, society, which further in our research will stand as basic conceptospheres. Undoubtedly the conceptosphere of the “Muslim world” concept can be formed and extended by other cognitive features, however in our study we will stuck to three above mentioned conceptospheres that will allow us explore the “Muslim world” concept from three different dimensions.

According to Russian 21st century linguist Marina Kozyreva, besides obligatory features, there are optional features of the concept “Muslim World”. According to her, among optional features on the basis of linguistic facts` analysis, there can be distinguished:

1) “Spiritual or material world of Islam”, correlates of which are spiritual values (Allah, prophets, jihad, hajj, namaz, shariah, etc.) or material values of Islam (household items, clothing, architectural monuments, etc). However, “this optional semantic feature is a modification of the basic meaning of the concept” [11, 2004] and more reflects the national specificity of the concept.

2) "Attitude" and "Evaluation" are in turn divided into "Positive" and "Negative".

The worldview, being a conceptual correlate of the feature “Attitude”, is expressed not only on religious, but also on ethnic grounds. The optional feature “Attitude” is a certain inner state and is actualized by the corrective activity of the mind. However, this process is not always available to outer eyes and does not always lie on the surface, which allows us to define the sign of “Attitude” as an optional feature of the concept.

Judgment is a conceptual correlation of the optional feature “Evaluation”, which can be combined with both the defense of Islam and the manifestation of negativity, with terrorism and Islamophobia [8, 2018]. The selected attribute “Evaluation” is indicated by us as an optional component, since it is an individual physiological reaction and can manifest itself depending on these or those external factors.

In view of the above stated information, this study will further focus on the following structure of the “Muslim world” concept (Figure 1):

Figure 1. "Muslim World" Concept Structure

CONCLUSION.

Proceeding from such a structure, the concept "Muslim World" can be analyzed in terms of nomination, evaluation and perception of it in modern English-speaking society. As it was mentioned above, the definitive analysis of language units reveals only part of the conceptual fields. The concept "Muslim World" can be studied further taking into consideration the concept verbalizers.

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